

Paramakudi, and Cotton Research Station, Srivilliputtur, Tamil Nadu, India. The crop was directly sown and maintained under rainfed condition up to 45 d after sowing, at which time the crop was irrigated. Plots were 3-m rows with 15 plants each at 30- × 20-cm row and plant spacing. Among the many physiological indices available, the most reliable, such as root weight and biomass productivity, were used to measure drought. Five competitive plants were randomly selected from each plot for observation and analysis.

Among the six parents tested, PMK1 (P3) was the superior general combiner for special drought characters (root weight, biomass productivity, plant height, and earliness). TKM9 (P1) for grain yield and IR64 (P4) for productive tillers were good general combiners. PMK1 (P3), a good combiner for all traits except grain yield and productive tillers, and IR64, a poor combiner for many characters, were crossed and showed positive significant SCA effects for all traits studied (see table). This shows that superior hybrids may also be obtained

from high/low GCA parental combinations. After PMK1/IR64, hybrids AS26556 (good combiner)/PMK1 (good combiner) and TKM9 (medium combiner)/PMK1 (good combiner) were next in superiority.

The differential combining ability of PMK1 with other parental types reveals that using this genotype as a potential parent in breeding programs to develop semidry-tolerant types may produce useful transgressive segregants in the segregating generation. ■

Combining ability of some varieties for grain quality traits in diallel mating system

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We evaluated six popular high-yielding rice genotypes (IR50, TKM9, ADT37, ADT39, ADT40, and Improved White

Ponni) and their 15 F₁ hybrids obtained through diallel mating (without reciprocals) for combining ability of 10 grain quality traits.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design during 1993 dry season and replicated three times. Hills were spaced at 20 × 10 cm, with a single seedling per hill. Five plants per replication were evaluated following standard procedures for 10 grain quality traits:

kernel length, kernel breadth, kernel thickness, L-B ratio, kernel length after cooking, kernel breadth after cooking, linear elongation ratio, breadthwise expansion ratio, hulling, and milling.

The variances due to general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) were significant except for kernel length. This indicated that the genotypes differed widely for the traits studied. Higher GCA variance than SCA

Table 1. Analysis of variance for combining ability.

Source of variation	df	Mean squares									
		Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Kernel thickness (mm)	L:B	Kernel length after cooking (mm)	Kernel breadth after cooking (mm)	Linear elongation ratio	Breadthwise expansion ratio	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)
General combining ability (GCA)	5	0.205***	0.205**	0.046**	0.378**	0.368**	0.094**	0.011**	0.018**	3.874**	4.037**
Specific combining ability (SCA)	15	0.005	0.005**	0.016**	0.160**	0.374**	0.042**	0.011**	0.015**	2.601**	2.648**
Error	40	0.016	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.011

*** = significant at 1% level.

Table 2. Estimates of general combining ability effects of parents for different grain quality traits.

Parent	Trait									
	Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Kernel thickness (mm)	L:B	Kernel length after cooking (mm)	Kernel breadth after cooking (mm)	Linear elongation ratio	Breadthwise expansion ratio	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)
IR50	0.09**	-0.22**	-0.01**	0.29**	0.40**	-0.03**	0.01**	0.06**	-0.43**	-0.33**
ADT37	-0.18**	0.15**	0.02**	-0.32**	-0.14**	0.21**	0.06**	-0.02**	0.37**	0.70**
TKM9	0.01	0.16**	0.05**	-0.04**	0.05**	-0.04**	-0.01	-0.07**	0.03**	-0.34**
ADT39	0.02	-0.05**	-0.07**	0.15**	-0.07**	0.01	0.01	0.02**	1.19**	1.08**
ADT40	0.06	0.10**	0.10**	-0.15**	-0.02	-0.04**	-0.05**	-0.02**	-0.52**	-0.49**
Improved White Ponni	0.01	-0.14**	-0.10**	0.07**	-0.21**	-0.11**	-0.02**	0.03**	-0.64**	-0.63**
SE (g)	0.041	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.014	0.010	0.004	0.004	0.035	0.034

** = significant at 1 and 5% level, respectively.

variance for all the traits (except kernel length after cooking and linear elongation ratio) indicated the predominance of additive gene action (Table 1).

IR50 possessed desirable GCA effects for kernel length, kernel breadth, kernel

thickness, L-B ratio, kernel length after cooking, kernel breadth after cooking, and linear elongation ratio. IR50 was found to be the best parent because of its desirable GCA effects for five traits (Table 2). ADT39 was the next best

parent. IR50 and ADT39 could be used in hybridization programs for improving grain quality traits through recombination breeding and for getting desirable segregants. ■

Breeding methods

Heterosis for kernel characters in rice

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Information is limited on the extent of heterosis for kernel characters in rice. We studied the heterotic manifestations of four kernel characters in 15 hybrids involving eight parents.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during 1991-92 wet season (Oct-Feb) at TNRRI. Each genotype (parents and hybrids) was planted in two 3-m rows at 30- × 20-cm spacing. Observations were recorded for 10 randomly selected plants per replication.

Seeds were hulled in a McGill sample sheller. Kernel length and L-B ratio were measured with a Mitutoyo micrometer. Grain was milled in a Kett rice polisher and cooked by the method of Juliano and Perez. Kernel elongation was computed as the ratio of mean length of cooked rice to that of milled rice. The performance of hybrids over mid-parent (di) and better parent (dii) was estimated following standard procedures.

Heterosis for kernel length was low. Improved White Ponni/ADT41 and IR50/Kasturi expressed significant and positive relative heterosis. Heterosis for kernel L-B ratio was significant and negative, indicating that none of the hybrids were superior for grain fineness. Relative heterosis for kernel length after cooking was positive and significant in five crosses. Heterosis over mid-parent and better parent for kernel elongation was positive and highly significant in six hybrids (see table).

Relative heterosis (di) and heterobeltiosis (dii) in % for kernel characters in selected crosses.^a TNRRI, Aduthurai, India. 1991-92 wet season.

Cross	Kernel length		Kernel L:B ratio		Kernel length after cooking		Kernel elongation	
	di	dii	di	dii	di	dii	di	dii
ADT37/ADT41	-3.1**	-22.1**	-11.4**	-36.9**	2.7*	-16.6**	9.2**	5.2**
ADT39/ADT41	-1.9**	-17.2**	-6.8**	-26.0**	1.4	-14.2**	4.0**	3.3*
ADT39/Kasturi	-2.6**	-16.0**	-11.5**	-29.3**	2.8*	-11.2**	8.8**	8.8**
IR50/Kasturi	0.7*	-5.6**	-5.1**	-15.6**	12.5**	-4.4**	12.2**	11.5**
Improved White Ponni/ADT41	1.9**	-14.7**	-4.1**	-21.5**	13.2**	-3.6**	11.9**	11.9**
Improved White Ponni/Kasturi	-1.2**	-15.5**	-9.2**	-25.2**	3.6*	-9.9**	8.0**	7.3**

*, ** = significant at 1 and 5% level, respectively.

IR50/Kasturi and Improved White Ponni/ADT41 show promise for improving kernel length, kernel length after cooking, and kernel elongation through heterosis breeding. ■

High-yielding somaclonal variants of Basmati 370

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Improving basmati varieties through cross breeding results in recombination of various genes for yield and quality. But

these new combinations often do not yield the desired basmati quality. We have been researching ways to accelerate the improvement of both quality and yield of basmati rices.

We obtained a series of somaclonal variants with desired characteristics. Seeds of Basmati 370 were inoculated on MS medium with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter. Calli were subcultured 12 times on the same

Table 1. Agronomic performance of somaclonal variants.^a NARC, Islamabad, Pakistan.

Variant	Flowering (d)		Plant height (cm)		Tillers/hill (no.)		1,000-grain weight (g)		Fertility (%)	Yield (t/ha)
TF4	114	de	120	f	12	e	17.33	cd	89.0	a
SN85	127	b	140	c	14	cd	16.00	de	65.0	de
SN1-80	129	ab	147	b	14	cd	14.33	e	65.0	de
TF11	115	de	116	g	15	bc	13.67	e	63.3	de
SN12	116	cd	113	h	13	de	19.00	abc	70.0	c
TF8	113	e	123	e	13	de	17.67	bcd	65.0	de
TF9	116	cd	127	d	20	a	17.33	cd	66.3	cd
TF10	118	c	123	e	16	b	16.00	de	61.7	e
Basmati 385	114	de	122	e	15	bc	21.00	a	80.0	b
Basmati 370	130	a	150	a	9	f	20.00	ab	70.0	c
LSD (5%)	2.142		2.187		1.265		2.38		3.514	0.5868
CV (%)	1.05		0.99		5.23		8.08		2.95	9.90

^aMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.